

Determination of dissociation constants of salicylic acids and stability constants of complexes of these ligands with copper(II), beryllium(II) and iron(III) ions : Correlation of dissociation and stability constants with molecular descriptors

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Abstract : Salicylic acid and its various derivatives have anti-rheumatic and antifungal action on human body. Dissociation constants of salicylic acid, *o*-/*m*-/*p*-cresotic acids and sulphosalicylic acid and stability constants of complexes of these ligands with Cu^{II}, Be^{II} ions were determined pH metrically and Fe^{III} ion were determined spectrophotometrically. A quantitative structure relationship of stability/dissociation constant of the compounds with molecular properties were considered, which include molecular weight, surface tension, index of refraction and density. The biological action of these compounds vary with the substituent present in the ring.

Keywords : Dissociation constant, stability constant, copper(II), beryllium(II), iron(III).

Introduction

Salicylic acid and its various derivatives have anti-rheumatic and antifungal actions on human body. The biological actions of these compounds vary with the substituent present in the ring. The introduction of a methyl group increases oxygen consumption but rate depends on the position of methyl group in the ring¹. A relationship between structure and activity has been sought by several workers to formulate the guideline for various biological effects of this class of compounds².

In order to study the structure action relationship, among salicylic acid and its various substituted derivatives, the dissociation constant of both, carboxylic acid group as well as phenolic group along with stability constant of these compounds with metals like Cu, Be and Fe were determined. While selecting the substituted derivative of salicylic acid, both types of substitution like electron-donor group and electron-withdrawing group were taken into consideration. The structures of these compounds are shown in Fig. 1.

The quantitative structure-relationship of stability constant/dissociation constant of the compounds with the molecular properties, which were considered, include molecular weight (MW), surface tension (ST), index of refraction (IR) and density (D).

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

On the basis of results of regression analysis that are reported in Tables 1 to 5, it is quite clear that both the stability constant ($\log k_1$) and dissociation constants pK_1 , pK_2 are significantly correlated with density, IR, MW, ST and in general any increase in the value of these structural indices will cause a decrease in pK value. This clearly

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Note

Table 1. Regression analysis for pK_1 values

Molecular properties	R	R ²	R ² _A	S.E.	F	Equation
D	0.957	0.915	0.887	0.287132	32.414	18.489 – 4.021 (±2.348) D
IR	0.967	0.936	0.914	0.250436	43.548	74.686 – 38.069 (±18.358) IR
MW	0.852	0.725	0.634	0.516934	7.926	17.0852 – 30 × 10 ⁻³ (±2.26 × 10 ²) MW
ST	0.965	0.930	0.902	0.260131	40.147	17.608 – 6.61 × 10 ⁻² (±6.52 × 10 ²) ST

R → Coefficient of correlation, R² → coefficient of determination, R²_A → adjusted R², S.E. → standard error of estimate, F → F ratio.

Table 2. Results obtained with respect to pK_2 values

Molecular properties	R	R ²	R ² _A	S.E.	F	Equation
D	0.977	0.954	0.938	0.256837	61.862	23.107 – 4.969 (±2.011) D
IR	0.983	0.986	0.955	0.219532	85.780	91.597 – 46.834 (±16.090) IR
MW	0.878	0.771	0.695	0.571519	10.099	20.750 – 2.87 × 10 ² (±2.28 × 10 ²) MW
ST	0.983	0.966	0.955	0.220370	85.106	21.391 – 8.15 × 10 ² (±8.04 × 10 ²) ST

Statistical data : same as in Table 1.

Table 3. Results obtained with respect to $\log k_1$ (Be^{II})

Molecular properties	R	R ²	R ² _A	S.E.	F	Equation
D	0.957	0.915	0.887	0.287132	32.414	16.539 – 2.772 (±0.937) D
IR	0.980	0.961	0.948	0.131022	73.469	54.330 – 25.868 (±9.604) IR
MW	0.903	0.816	0.755	0.283823	13.296	15.280 – 1.63 × 10 ² (±0.015) MW
ST	0.986	0.972	0.962	0.111502	102.585	15.570 – 4.53 × 10 ⁻² (±0.014) ST

Statistical data : same as in Table 1.

Table 4. Results with respect to $\log k_1$ (Cu^{II})

Molecular properties	R	R ²	R ² _A	S.E.	F	Equation
D	0.878	0.770	0.694	0.273468	10.050	13.388 – 2.133 (±2.140) D
IR	0.930	0.865	0.820	0.209787	19.180	44.502 – 21.167 (±15.378) IR
MW	0.867	0.487	0.316	0.408756	2.845	12.144 – 1.09 × 10 ⁻² (±0.021) MW
ST	0.903	0.815	0.253	0.245424	13.212	12.70 – 3.58 × 10 ⁻² (±0.032) ST

Statistical data : same as in Table 1.

Table 5. Results with respect to $\log k_1$ (Fe^{III})

Molecular properties	R	R ²	R ² _A	S.E.	F	Equation
D	0.981	0.962	0.950	0.205745	76.708	22.422 – 4.433 (±1.611) D
IR	0.980	0.960	0.946	0.212854	7.473	82.989 – 41.449 (±15.603) IR
MW	0.897	0.740	0.740	0.468356	12.382	20.391 – 2.60 × 10 ⁻² (±0.024) MW
ST	0.984	0.958	0.958	0.188857	91.601	20.876 – 7.24 × 10 ⁻² (±0.025) ST

Statistical data : same as in Table 1.

indicates that as the dilution increases, the ease of reaction increases and therefore, biological actions related to these compounds will thus be affected.

Table 6 shows that in the case of *o*-cresotic acid, due to intramolecular H-bonding, dissociation constant of phenolic -OH is decreased. This may be due to the fact that

Table 6

Acids	Dissociation constant of phenolic OH (pK ₁) and of carboxylic COOH (pK ₂)		Stability constants (log k ₁) for		
	pK ₁	pK ₂	Cu ^{II}	Be ^{II}	Fe ^{III}
SA	13.24	16.05	10.12	12.66	16.20
<i>m</i> -CA	13.54	16.48	10.63	12.82	16.46
<i>p</i> -CA	13.784	16.98	10.93	12.92	16.65
<i>o</i> -CA	14.14	16.61	10.54	13.09	16.92
SSA	11.90	14.34	9.66	11.64	14.59

Table 7

Sl. no.	Molecular properties	SA	<i>o</i> -CA/ <i>m</i> -CA/ <i>p</i> -CA	SSA
1.	Molecular formula (MA)	C ₇ H ₆ O ₃	C ₈ H ₈ O ₃	C ₇ H ₆ O ₆ S
2.	Molecular weight (MW)	138.121	152.147	218.185
3.	Index of refraction (IOR)	1.615	1.599	1.649
4.	Surface tension (ST) (in dyne/cm)	64.4	58.000	86.80
5.	Density (D) (in g/cm ³)	1.375	1.304	1.771

oxygen of '-OH' group becomes more negative due to +I effect of '-CH₃' at *ortho*-position, which in turn may be the cause of increase in oxygen consumption. Similar investigations related to the effect of alkyl substitution of salicylic acid, specially the *ortho* derivatives were done by Stuart *et al.*³.

Regression analysis results of molecular descriptors with respect to log k₁ values for Be^{II} complexes (Table 3) shows maximum agreement. Lower density correlation for Cu^{II} complexes (Table 4) may indicate the cause of the presence of Cu in trace amounts in our biological system, since they may be toxic in their higher concentrations. The inverse relationship of log k₁ of Fe^{III} complexes with molecular descriptors shows that Fe^{II} is more favourable to our biological system than Fe^{III}. This is true in the case of haemoglobin, which involves Fe^{II} ion in forming complex and not Fe^{III}.

Experimental

The ligands used in the present work were salicylic acid (E. Merck), *o*-cresotic acid, *m*-cresotic acid, *p*-cresotic acid (K and K Laboratories) and sulphosalicylic acid (E. Merck). All these ligands were purified by recrystallization. The analytical grade salts of Cu^{II}, Be^{II} and Fe^{III} were used. The pK values of carboxylic and phenolic groups were determined by spectrophotometric method⁴. The spectrophotometry was also used for determination of stability constant (log k₁) of Fe^{III} complexes of 1 : 1 metal salicylate⁵.

The stability constant (log k₁) of Cu^{II} and Be^{II} complexes of various derivatives of salicylic acid were determined by pH titration technique using the method described elsewhere⁶. The values of dissociation constant and metal ligand stability constant thus determined are given in Table 6. The data obtained by CHEMDRAW analysis for the molecular properties are given in Table 7. Regression analysis was done with the help of SPSS programming to establish relation between structural parameters and pK₁, pK₂ and log k₁ values. Correlation established between molecular properties (independent variable) with pK values of acids and log k₁ values of chosen metal ions Cu^{II}, Be^{II} and Fe^{III} (dependant variables) are shown in Tables 1-5.

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